

Political Affects and Collective Action in Times of Crisis

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Transversal Political Affects and Shared Inner Experience: From Acts of Disobedience to the Institution of Multitude

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Ephemeral collectivities that emerge in times of crises are one of those rare socio-ontological occurrences that suspend the classical opposition between individualism and holism. Protests, blockades, strikes, uprisings, mass actions of solidarity and diverse radical democratic practices that constitute them, blur the rigid boundaries between the individuals and the group and/or the subjects and the society as decisively separate modes of being. By that token, they are opening a space for what is to be named the becoming of multitudes. Thus, this article will commence with an overlook of Gilles Deleuze's distinction between becoming and history, and more generally of his theory of events. In that sense, Deleuze's hypothesis claiming that "What history grasps in an event is the way it's actualized in particular circumstances; the event's becoming is beyond the scope of history" (Deleuze 1990) will be superposed on the example of ongoing protests in Serbia.

Furthermore, we will conceptualize and examine two sorts of phenomena that appear in this kind of historically disruptive events: transversal political affects and shared inner experience. In that aim, we will engage with philosophies of two presumably very different authors: Baruch Spinoza and Georges Bataille. In the first section, we will employ Spinoza's theory of affects, in order to define "transversal political affects" – a specific kind of affects that take place on the transindividual plane, such as described by Gilles Deleuze, Étienne Balibar, or more recently Jason Read. More concretely, we will see how these political affects take place in protest and other acts of civil disobedience, thus dissolving the preexisting identarian formations. In the second section, the article will focus on Bataille's concept of inner experience, arguing that the latter could be understood as a shared phenomenon, challenging the opposition inside/outside, that seem to crumble under the intensity of collective disobedience. We will see how the notions of excess, sacrifice, ecstasy, horror and delight – all central to Bataille's philosophy – appear in concrete political contexts, thus contesting dominant authorities by articulating the politics of the impossible, as Jean-Michel Besnier puts it following Bataille. The final, third section, raises the question of possibility of instituting these ephemeral collectivities. We will propose therefore to look at the latter through the lens of the notion of multitude, such as it appears in Spinoza, but also with thinkers inspired by him, such as Antonio Negri, Alexandre Matheron, Paolo Virno and others. Throughout the article, theoretical hypothesis will be illustrated by examples from history, literature and art, with a particular attention to the current social uprising taking place in Serbia.

Aesthetic Communication

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Seeking to overcome the view of the public sector as a depoliticized apparatus – and of civil society collectives as outside of governance – this chapter is about the role of aesthetic affectivity in the building or the undermining of sustainable communities of care.

The general framework is a paradigm of care that, coming from tradition of critical and cultural-historical psychology, hopes to unite a dynamic ontology of collectives and of subjects with an emphasis on conceptualizing their emergence, envelopment and sustenance, through processes of recognition. This approach is relevant as an alternative to a currently hegemonic dichotomy of institutionalized standardization vs. ephemeral aesthetization in the representation and governance of care practices and collectives.

My recent background, as unfolded in my 2023 book *Rearticulating Motives*, are close studies of aesthetic activities as part of practices that sought beyond narrow treatment standards toward a wider care for young drug users. Aesthetic theories (Rancière, Stenner, and others) helped conceptualize art, not as a means (to cure or to recognition), nor as an end in itself, but as ways of rearticulating and reframing activities and their motives, by creating and contemplating *dissensus*, i.e. diverging ways of making sense, of relating the sensuous with the sensible. The materiality of artworks evokes an indeterminate affectivity that corresponds with liminal moments in processes of reframing, which can reconfigure the distributions of in-/capacities.

However, this ‘democratic’ potential of art has a counterpart in what we might call the ‘dark side’ of aesthetics. With this chapter, I venture to understand this aspect further, hoping to expand the analyses of the politics of aesthetics in welfare practices – and perhaps beyond them. For this purpose, I take up lessons from classics in critical theory (Brecht, Bloch, Adorno) about the aesthetics of fascism. Specifically, the concepts of mimesis and identification appear relevant to understanding how aesthetic re-/presentations can play a part in dominance and subjection.

Finally, this connects to the issue of ephemerality: Probably authoritative identification, although appealing to essential universals, mostly works as a way of redirecting liminality toward disruption, undermining the slow growth of democratic communities of care. Authoritarian collectives are weak and volatile, at once resting on and perpetually tearing down, devouring, the standards easily available in consumer society. And accepting ephemerality as a descriptor of a given domain of social interaction may imply both ignoring authoritarian tendencies and overlooking tendencies toward cultivating care.

Subject of Rupture: Dislocation, Hegemony, and the Formation of Political Agency

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This article seeks to conceptualize the process through which forms of subjectivity and social relations that aim to transform dominant social structures emerge during periods of crisis. We focus on the interrelationship between discursive and affective processes in shaping political subjectivities oriented towards social change.

We understand social structures as discursive formations, drawing on Lacan's concept of the symbolic order and Laclau's theory of hegemony. Social structures consist of differential elements whose meaning is determined through a particular code, unified by a "master signifier" that organizes the symbolic field and assigns meaning to its components. According to Laclau, symbolic orders are not grounded in necessity but arise from contingent historical circumstances, rendering them inherently unstable and incomplete. Hegemony operates by masking this contingency: through the articulation of a master signifier, the symbolic order is presented as necessary, thereby concealing its constructed origins.

In Lacanian terms, the master signifier corresponds to the big Other—the symbolic order itself, as it is represented to the subject. The symbolic order is inherently marked by a lack, not due to internal inconsistency, but because it lacks metaphysical foundation. As Laclau argues, the master signifier is established through a "decision" at a specific moment, which founds a social order and grants it temporary coherence. This decision is enacted by the subject, who mediates between competing symbolic configurations and forms a chain of equivalence among discursive elements by positing a new master signifier. In doing so, the subject plays a constitutive role in rearticulating the social field in response to the disintegration of a previous hegemony.

We interpret moments of crisis as instances of "dislocation" (Laclau), when the symbolic order confronts its limits and reveals its contingent foundations. These moments coincide with the subject's recognition of the lack within the big Other—a lack that echoes the subject's own and opens a space for political intervention. In this space, the symbolic order can be apprehended not as fixed or natural, but as a product of the subject's own discursive practice.

To theorize this process further, we draw on Freud's notion of group formation, based on a shared libidinal investment in a common ego ideal, and Laclau's concept of myth, understood as an emergent discursive space that represents the dislocated elements in

a new way. Subject formation, in this context, is conceived as a political act that mediates between the collapse of a hegemonic structure and the emergence of a new one. By articulating a new master signifier, the subject reconfigures the symbolic order, instituting a new, though still contingent, social totality.

A review of the traces of memory in social movements studies

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Social movements challenge the interpretation of a society's core values and aim to transform it (Touraine, 1985). They also reshape the individuals who participate in them (Melucci, 2003), not only during periods of intense mobilization but also during more introspective phases, when activists reflect on and process their experiences. While most research in social movement studies has centred on political processes, strategic interactions, and the framing of demands, this work places particular emphasis on the subjectivity of the actors involved (Melucci, 2003; Pleyers, 2025; Scribano, 2011).

Within the field of social movement studies, the intersection with memory studies has highlighted the emergence of urban memory as expressed through social interactions, collective action, and movement identities (Badilla, 2020). Social movements, collective memory, and activism are deeply interconnected (López et al., 2024). As Kubal and Becerra (2014) argue, social movements play an important role in shaping collective memory. They are often imbued with political and moral significance, sustaining challenges to political and cultural authority and drawing on memory to establish legitimacy and a sense of identity rooted in continuity with the past.

This chapitre proposal explores the role of social movements in transmitting collective memory. It involves an extensive literature review on how the study of social movements has engaged with the study of memory, with particular emphasis on how emotions are addressed in memory transmission processes.

Through a qualitative study, the author has begun to demonstrate links between student and feminist social movements in Chile and the intergenerational transmission of collective memory related to the dictatorship. This memory circulates between generations born in democracy and their relatives or close contacts who lived through the dictatorship. The study delves into how social movements facilitate the articulation of previously silenced histories, fostering intergenerational dialogue. It also highlights how Chilean society continues to be shaped by the legacy of dictatorship-era violence, with social movements playing a key role in confronting historical silences and shaping collective memory.

Based on these findings, the author poses the following questions: In what other contexts do similar situations arise? Under what conditions can social movements—whose primary demands are not directly related to memory—nonetheless contribute to its transmission?

What role do the subjectivity and subjectification of the actors involved in these movements play in the processes of memory transmission?

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Protests as Interruptions: Understanding Social Change in the Here and Now

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Recent forms of collective resistance, such as those seen roughly 2010–2025 (e.g., the student-led protests in Serbia, Gezi Park protests, Black Lives Matter protests in the United States, protests in Iran following the death of Mahsa Amini), represent a stark departure from the traditional methods of protest. These collective acts of resistance are reactionary to the rise of authoritarian regimes and the lack of trust in the representatives that operate within the existing system of governance. They are often described as "spontaneous," "leaderless," and "horizontally" organized, where participants reject formal leadership and institutionalized political structures. We are witnessing a break with the traditional protests that can be characterized as leftist, progressionist, and revolutionist, and a shift towards a general rejection of state-based politics and its forms of representation, a lack of ideological unity, and a positive focus on world-building practices as an alternative to traditional political organizing. In light of this transformation, what is the role and function of collective political action?

Rather than pursuing a goal of political representation, these recent protests aim to disrupt and dismantle existing systems of power through direct action and non-representative means. Existing critiques of recent protests and movements are indicative of a shift in the aims and ends of collective action as well as in its temporality over the past decade and a half, which require an updated set of parameters and assumptions that are more suitable for our current moment through which we can make better sense of recent collective action. Although they are criticized for not being generative because they lack clear political demands and a vision for a "better future" shared by their participants, looking at them from a perspective that acknowledges this break with the traditional protests would allow us to see their generative and transformative potential.

To better understand recent forms of collective action, we propose a theoretical framing of protests as *interruptions* of the current moment, spaces, and the status quo. Through this framing, we shift the focus to the *here and now* rather than a nebulous future where social and political change is hoped for, as well as to the ephemeral moment of protests in which new relations are built, and opportunities for feeling, acting, and becoming appear. In this paper, we lay out this framing by theorizing the micro-dynamics of resistive collective action. We first introduce a radical societal crisis as an initiating event which

collectively disturbs members of society. We then conceptualize the dynamics of rising collective action through the following interconnected dimensions: temporality, spatiality and affectivity. Further, we argue that moments of interruption bring about forms of political subjectivity which do not precede but *emerge from* them. Political subjectivity, arising through the affectively charged and shared presence of being and acting together in public spaces during interrupted time, is the carrier of what is referred to as social change. This framing allows us to conceptualize change from within collective action, and not as an effect that takes place after it.

Evaluating the (anti)democratic productivity of interactional disruption

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From theoretical developments on Goffman's interaction order, and empirical investigations of civic practices in Western Europe and the USA, we would like to propose a joint reflection on the productions of interactional troubles and disruptions, and the evaluation of their (anti)democratic effects. In a recent text, Iddo Tavory and Gary A. Fine (2020) expose some of the limits of the Goffmanian interaction order. Overly fixated on alignment and correction to account for the dynamics of ordinary sociability, it is all the more so for apprehending political interactions in a regime of democratic pluralism. Tavory and Fine show the social productivity of interactional involvements in which they observe not so much a "disruption of interaction" as a "disruption for interaction". For example, breaking with politeness or small talk to get to the heart of the matter; raising trouble or even provoking it, to initiate problematizing interactions through discussion or inquiry, which corresponds to conceptions of democratic interaction held by authors such as John Dewey or Jurgen Habermas — for the latter, "communicative action" is not a smooth process, and may require a break from Goffmanian "dramaturgical action" (Habermas, 1984). Mathieu Berger's ethnography of the interactional "havoc" caused by streams of hostile, obscene, or absurd comments from radical and deliberately disorderly speakers at Los Angeles City Council meetings draws attention to another "productive" aspect of disruption (Berger, 2020). This production can be understood in terms of the "manufacture of negative experience" (Goffman, 1974), and beyond, in terms of "careers" of deviation and alienation that involve not only the individuals causing the trouble, but also — as Goffman argues in "Insanity of Place" (1969) — the troubled community. This alternative conception of the productivity of disorder reminds us that Goffman not only allows us to think about the negativity of certain disruptions — beyond their mere sterility — but also to understand them according to temporalities that are no longer those of instant micro-events, momentary incidents, but rather of repeated havoc that has become habitual and predictable, shaping the frame of the city council in a lasting way. In other words, rather than an event or a figure, disruption now qualifies the ground of these situations, and their overall tone.

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The Emotion of Being Moved and Reorganization of Hierarchy of Values in Crisis

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In this presentation, I continue the earlier work on the significance of shared emotions during crisis, by addressing the emotion of being moved and its function in crisis situation.

Previously, we argued that crises create a rupture in both cognitive and emotional forms of sharing, but also open up a space of possibilities for the reorganization of values, as well as the formation of new collectives and plural agency. A crucial element in this process are calls of social engagement among actors, particularly in relation to trust – both in other actors and in potential for restructuring the community (see Cvejić, Ivković, Prodanović 2021, cf. Helm 2017, Ratcliffe 2024).

Building on this, I explore the potential significance of emotion of being moved in crisis situation– such as reactions to heroic acts. Following Cova and Deonna, I treat being moved as a distinct emotion, characterized by specific phenomenology, physiology, function and formal object. They argue that situations evoking this emotion are “instances in which positive values are brought to the fore and manifest themselves in a particularly salient way” (Cova, Deonna 2014: 453). Accordingly, the formal object of being moved can be described as “a certain positive value standing out” (ibid.: 454). This emotion reminds us of values we hold most dear. Its function, they argue, “consists in the reorganization of one’s hierarchy of values and priorities” (ibid: 458), and it also serves a social function, “power to reinforce the links that tie a community together by signaling to its members the importance that a given individual attaches to the most fundamental values sustaining that community” (ibid: 459). I have argued elsewhere that being moved is particularly important in situations of social change, as it expresses a readiness to reorganize the hierarchy of values in the light of new circumstances of mutual dependency (Cvejić 2023).

Additionally, I will examine the example of emotion of being moved in response to student protests in Serbia. Through this example, I will address the theoretical question of the sharedness of these emotions. I argue that while reactions of *being moved* in crisis situations are typically individual and may not meet the criteria for shared emotions (Leon, Szanto & Zahavi 2017), they nonetheless express readiness and motivation to reinforce the links that tie a community together. In other words, the political significance of this emotion, in reorganization of hierarchy of values, is strongly tied to a possibility to meet conditions of plurality and integration, as well as a link to a collective action.

Anticipation, Crisis and Transformative Groups

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In my talk, I will continue the exploration of the constitution of “transformative groups” during the times of crisis, focusing particularly on the role of anticipation. By a “transformative group,” I refer to a collective formed in response to crisis conditions characterized by a lack of clear articulation of ongoing events and the absence of apparent solutions or agents addressing these events, resulting in a state of global disorientation (Nikolić 2024). In crisis, normal anticipations that guide social interactions fail, necessitating new forms of reliance and cooperation among diverse individuals (Cvejić et. al. 2023). This exploration aims to elucidate the conditions under which transformative groups can not only emerge but also sustain themselves and effectively drive social change, and the extent to which these observations may be translated into concrete guidelines for political action.

Throughout the analysis, I will use a Husserlian model of the dynamical relationship between anticipations, their fulfillment and disappointment, applied to social relations and interactions. My hypothesis is that fulfillment and disappointment of anticipations constantly occur in the normal, everyday flow of life, and fundamentally structure social reality for each individual. In contrast to conditions of normalcy, a crisis entails a significant disruption of shared anticipatory frameworks concerning the basic functioning of the social world, impacting a broad segment of the population. This modifies anticipations of everyone affected by bringing in a new level of uncertainty: we are not sure what we can anticipate anymore. We are collectively aware that we cannot really rely on our anticipations of the future, because the world does not function in a predictable way anymore.

I will apply the theoretical insights from my previous work on the current political crisis in Serbia and the analysis of the formation of a new kind of collective political agent: citizen assemblies. I will draw on my own direct experience of active participation in a local citizen assembly over the past 3 months, starting from its formation. I will analyze the formation of the group identity, and the dynamic of fulfillment and disappointment as they unfolded through the concrete actions undertaken by the assembly. The anticipation of the number of participants, as well as the fulfillment/disappointment thereof will turn out to be an important additional aspect to be considered.

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Group Agents and the Sincerity Condition on Blame and Praise

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Blame and praise are important drivers of social change, and, given their power and influence, group agents such as states, corporations and universities could play an important role by partaking in this practice. However, there often seems something 'off' about blame- or praise-interactions that involve group agents. I argue that in many cases the problem seems to be that the group agent is insincere, because their engaging in this practice seems to serve some ulterior purpose. In this paper, I argue in favor of the Sincerity Condition on praise and blame: The blame- or praise-interaction is appropriate only if the blame or praise is expressed for the right sort of reason. And I investigate whether group agents can satisfy this sincerity condition.

First, I argue that insincere moral blame is distinct from disproportionate, unwarranted, hypocritical, complicit, or meddling blame. I show that the target cases cannot be explained in terms of lacking standing, warrant or proportionality. The Sincerity Condition is an additional distinct condition on the appropriateness of blame-interactions. Second, I argue that insincere moral praise is distinct from patronizing, hypocritical or obstructionist praise. The lack of an appropriate motive for blame or praise alone can make the praise-interaction inappropriate. Finally, I argue that group agents with a high degree of corporate moral concern can in principle satisfy the sincerity condition. Corporate moral concern requires having a substantive set of normatively informed member rules, procedural policies, and operational policies, which enables group agents to perform acts for moral reasons. This opens the door for sincere blame and praise. However, given that very few group agents exhibit adequate moral concern, it is unlikely that many group agents in current form will satisfy the Sincerity Condition.

Therapeutic trust as non-identity: how intersubjective relations can subvert capitalist structural domination

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In *Communities of Respect*, Bennet Helm defines 'therapeutic trust' as trust in others not based on evidence that they are trustworthy, such as the fact that we share with them a common horizon of norms, beliefs and commitments. In pronounced societal crises, when the general level of trust decreases due to what phenomenologists call the 'loss of the communal world', we may have therapeutic trust in others even as we distrust them conventionally. This paper elaborates my previous collaborative research on 'ephemeral collective affectivity' and social domination – ephemeral collective affectivity is a form of ephemeral intersubjectivity that takes shape in conditions of crisis, when a group of actors who do not share a common normative perspective start interacting through mutual 'calls of engagement' and establish a shared affective focus on the crisis and their own interdependence.

In the paper, I argue that relations of therapeutic trust in ephemeral collective affectivities have the potential to partially resocialize actors in a manner that allows for the subversion of, among other, one form of domination in capitalism that is difficult to challenge in normal circumstances: domination of people by the key capitalist social forms of value, commodity and capital. This form of domination affects our experience of the world - as Marx argued, it induces us to perceive the relational phenomenon of the value of a commodity in essentialist terms ('commodity fetishism'). Adorno elaborates this line of argument, claiming that social-form domination shapes our perception of all phenomena in such a way that their relational aspects are occluded - what he terms 'identity thinking'. I argue that this perspective can be applied to our experience of normative social groups, as social-form domination leads to 'normative identity fetishism', essentialization of aspects of people's identity rooted in membership in normative groups, which makes us prone to see these identities as unchangeable. However, due to their peculiar, forward-looking nature, relations of therapeutic trust in ephemeral collective affectivity have the potential to subvert these effects of social-form domination and turn around the direction of causation.

Emotions and Empowerment in the 15M Assemblies in Madrid

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The paper presents research on the public expression of emotions in the assemblies of the Spanish 15M movement and their role on participants' empowerment. I conducted fieldwork in Madrid over three years, from May 2011 to May 2014. I observed approximately sixty assemblies and carried out interviews with forty Indignados. The 15M assemblies are characterized by formalizing speaking and interacting rules, such as rotating roles in the assembly (facilitating, taking turns to speak, keeping minutes, etc.), introducing gesture-based language, decision-making by consensus, and so on. However, participation formalization is paralleled by public emotion expression. It involves a process of empowerment, based on the collective sharing of individual problems and emotions. This process contrasts with the “rise to generality”, based on the “force of the best argument” and expertise, as emphasized in deliberative democracy theories. I will show that all the 15M assemblies acted similarly, leaving ample room for addressing individual problems, without repressing the public expression of emotions. In doing so, it promotes the development of participants' empowerment, as they gradually become aware of both individual and collective capacity to change their daily lives.

The Role of Collective Affectivity in Civil Repair

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This study investigates the role of emotions in the student-led protest movement in Serbia, which erupted in December 2024 and evolved into a significant civic mobilization. Triggered by the collapse of the concrete canopy at the Novi Sad train station—an event that claimed 16 lives and was quickly framed as a symbol of systemic corruption and institutional neglect—the protests became a catalyst for broad-based demands for accountability and civil renewal.

Moving beyond the traditional view of emotions as irrational undercurrents in social life, this research adopts an interpretive sociological approach, foregrounding emotions as meaningful, constitutive forces in collective action. Drawing on Anna Durnová's work, the study understands emotions not merely as private experiences but as socially shared modes of sense-making, through which participants articulate grievances, define injustices, and generate legitimacy for their claims. Emotions are thus seen as central to the public narration of crises, shaping the very framework through which societal disruptions are interpreted and contested.

At the heart of the analysis is the concept of collective affectivity: the shared emotional orientations that coalesce around pivotal social events. Individual emotional experiences, when publicly expressed and socially validated, generate collective affectivity, which in turn sustains solidarity and energizes civic action. Rather than passive reflections of crisis, collective affectivities are active, relational processes that both mirror and constitute the evolving dynamics of the protest movement.

The study integrates civil sphere theory (Jeffrey Alexander) with the sociology of emotions, focusing on the emergence and transformation of collective affectivity during key episodes of protest. Specifically, it analyzes moments of heightened mobilization—Slavija (December 22), Autokomanda (January 27), Novi Sad (February 1–2), Kragujevac (February 15), Niš (March 1), Belgrade (March 15), and Novi Pazar (April 12)—conceptualized as “crystallization points” where affective energies intensify and civil solidarity is most visibly forged.

Through this lens, the protests are not merely responses to a crisis but are sites where emotions and meaning-making practices interact, creating the affective grounds for civil

repair. By illuminating how collective affectivity shapes and is shaped by public narratives of injustice and renewal, the study advances a cultural-sociological understanding of how societies confront and transform conditions of systemic failure. Emotions are thus reinterpreted as essential to the processes of societal critique and civic reconstruction, revealing the affective underpinnings of civil sphere resilience and change.

Intuition, Affects and the Political: The Formation of (Counter)Institutions in the Aftermath of Contingent Events

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This paper argues that modern sociology, while understanding societal risks on a macro level, overlooks the micro-dimensions of how individuals process contingent events. It proposes a micro-macro link, suggesting that shared intuitions and emotional responses to unpredictable crises can drive significant social change. Following tragic events, collective “affective atmospheres” can foster new political insights and lead to the formation of temporary (counter)institutions that challenge established norms. These ephemeral structures are vital for creating new forms of collective identity and shifting political loyalties. Drawing on the work of Summers-Effler and Collins, the paper highlights how emotional energy in social interactions builds solidarity and validates “deviant emotions,” fostering critical consciousness. When existing institutions fail to address new social meanings and expectations, these emotionally charged collective experiences can lay the groundwork for social movements. By focusing on everyday interactions and emotional responses to crises, the paper illuminates the transformative potential of micro-level intuitions and affects. It emphasizes their crucial, yet often underexplored, role in navigating social risks and driving social change.

Obsolete Affects: Archaism and Social Change

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Modernity is frequently conceived, following Marx and Engels, as an age in which “everything solid melts into air”—a time of accelerated, irreversible change demarcated from the premodern world, typically seen as governed by tradition, slow temporality, and communal belief systems. This binary framing has led many 19th and 20th century thinkers to treat modern and premodern modes of belief, behavior, and affectivity as fundamentally incommensurable. One notable example is Benjamin Constant’s critique of the French Revolution. He reproached the Jacobins—and, by extension, their intellectual forerunners such as Rousseau—for attempting to mobilize affects alien to modern sensibility. In Constant’s view, modern individuals are shaped by a different affective structure. The revolution’s recourse to terror, he argued, misunderstood the affective structure of modern society, resulting in destructive consequences.

This view of modernity as a radical rupture from the premodern has, however, been increasingly contested throughout the 20th century. Thinkers such as Lenin and Trotsky, with their theory of unequal and combined development, challenged the notion of linear social progress by showing how capitalist modernity continues to depend on pre-capitalist social forms. Similarly, Ernst Bloch’s notion of the *Gleichzeitigkeit des Ungleichzeitigen* (“simultaneity of the non-simultaneous”) captures the persistence of uneven temporal layers within modernity, a dynamic he used to interpret the rise of fascism. Deleuze and Guattari further elaborate on this by introducing the notion of “archaism”—a process through which capitalism recodes archaic patterns of desire, belief, and affectivity into its own functioning assemblages.

This proposal focuses on the archaism of affect under conditions of radical social transformation, particularly within revolutionary movements. Such moments often invoke the past—through language, imagery, and aesthetics—not merely to break from the present but to establish a different continuity with history capable of motivating and legitimizing collective action. My aim is to examine how affects are generated in contexts of temporal rupture, and how the past functions as a reservoir of affective intensities, reactivated and reconfigured in new assemblages. Specifically, I will focus on two affects—fear and courage—to explore how their archaic forms are translated, distorted, or repurposed in modern political and theoretical frameworks. For instance, Hobbesian fear is grounded in self-interested individualism, whereas premodern terror often had a

mythic and collective function, as seen in Polybius or Clastres. I will ask under what conditions this atomized fear might be transformed into a relational affect capable of supporting a politics of non-domination. Courage, similarly, has been sidelined in modern theory for its association with militarism and fanaticism, yet revolutionary movements repeatedly revive archaic models of courage as engines of social change. By employing Deleuze and Guattari's concepts of the "assemblage," I propose to trace how affects function differently depending on their degree and the structures in which they are embedded. In doing so, I aim to illuminate the layered temporalities of affect within modernity and the ambivalent legacy of its premodern inheritances.